

Safe And Decentralised Hydrogen Fuel Production And Storage For Residential Building And Mobility Applications

Artur Braun¹, Mmantsae M. Diale^{1,2}, Kelebogile D. Maabong^{1,2,3}, Rita Toth¹

¹*Empa. Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science & Technology, Dübendorf, Switzerland. E-mail: artur.braun@alumni.ethz.ch, rita.toth@empa.ch*

²*University of Pretoria, Pretoria, South Africa. E-mail: Mmantsae.Diale@up.ac.za*

³*University of Botswana, Gaborone, Botswana. E-mail: kelemaabong@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT: Large scale facilities pose a potential risk and threat because with one isolated attack large damage can be obtained, for example in a city, potentially with a large number of human casualties. We present a solar energy harvesting strategy which allows for the generation of fuel for housing and mobility in a decentralised form. A city or a part of a city cannot be shut down from energy supply by a terrorist attack on this energy generation and storage infrastructure, because it is virtually fully decentralised and independent (no electric grid). This system is based on photo-electrochemical cell technology and takes advantage of the solar energy arriving at small landscapes in local neighbourhoods in the range of few 100 sqm area per operation unit. The fuel is hydrogen, or hydrocarbons such as methane or methanol, when carbon dioxide greenhouse gas is included in the chemical process cycle. The necessary water for the process may come from the local sewage waste-water system. The problem of energy storage after finish of sunshine during the day is also solved by this technology, because a storable fuel is produced. The pronounced safety feature of this approach is that many small units are built, which are impossible to demolish in a terror strike, as opposed to single large industrial complexes which are very attractive for terrorists to attack because of the high destructive "efficiency" by a single plot, but also by the commensurate public attention and "terror", literally, which comes with the attack on a landmark scale facility. The negative part in this calculation comes from the loss of efficiency by moving from few large units to many small units. This is likely the price which society has to pay for the gain in safety from terrorism.

Keywords: fuel supply, solar hydrogen, decentralized, disaster, explosion

1. INTRODUCTION

Storage of energy in a central large installation poses a general risk for supply because one single accident, natural disaster or man-made attack or sabotage can destroy or defunct this installation. If this installation is the centre of an energy supply network, recipients of energy will be cut down from the consumption on this supply line (compare Walker 2013). Since we consider here a concentrated energy storage installation, we have also the risk that the quick explosive release of energy by such accident, disaster or attack has the potential of causing a large damage in property or even cause human fatalities. Prominent examples are thermal runaways of nuclear power plants with subsequent meltdown of their core (Chernobyl, Fukushima), explosions in gas power plants (PEMEX pipeline, plants and headquarters (Stratfor 2007, Navarro 2012, Knecht 2013, Reuters 2016)), failure of water dams (Banqiao Dam, (Svensson 1998)). Decentralized small scale energy supply systems are less prone to such risks (Schütze 2013).

Photovoltaics (PV) has become a mature electric energy supply technology which can provide small scale and large scale electric power in sunny regions during daytime. About 20% of the world energy use is in electric energy, which at least theoretically can be produced by PV. The other 80% are in all kinds of fuels (fossil, nuclear, biomass, other renewables including wind, water, and solar) (Thapper 2013). The storage of sunshine based electric PV energy for use overnight is supposedly a problem, but only a technical one, which will eventually be solved.

We present an alternative solution (compare Falkenstein-Smith 2016) which produces solar hydrogen fuel by water splitting in photoelectrochemical cells (Hu 2013). Photoelectrochemical cell (PEC) technology is based on the utilization of semiconductor photoelectrodes which are contained in aqueous electrolytes (basically waste water with additional ionic charge carriers) and then directly electrolyse the water into oxygen gas and hydrogen fuel when exposed to the sunlight. The continuous components which we need is thus the solar radiation from the sun as the primary energy source, and water. The photoelectrodes can be made from low cost metal oxide films which are coated on glass supports. Iron oxide, rust, basically, can be used for this purpose (Bora 2013) and has a solar-to-hydrogen efficiency of around 15%. 10 Watt per sqm is a realistic power output for PEC, but 50 W are projected for the future (Jung 2016). With a 100 sqm large rooftop installation we have a 1 kW "residential" power source which produces solar hydrogen fuel during the day which can be stored as gas and later used in fuel cells for electric power generation. This technology does not depend on an electric grid connection. The PEC reactor can have the shape of large panels similar like windows. The power output and thus energy supply scales with the extent of access to light, i.e. the claimable area in sqm.

2. CONSIDERATIONS FOR RESIDENTIAL FUEL PRODUCTION SYSTEM

A residential fuel production setting comparable to the conditions as outlined in the Introduction is shown Figure 1. There the rooftop is used for water collection and solar thermal water heating. This is a densely populated area in the city center of Bangalore, India. We notice rain water storage containers (black and blue upright cylinders) and a solar thermal water heating system (blue horizontal cylinder with “ramp” tube array). The entire roof top area can in principle be utilized for the deployment of a PEC reactor with window panel based electrodes for hydrogen production from water, which still allow for the use of the infrared radiation for solar thermal water heating underneath.

A large window type PEC reactor on the rooftop could be the decentralized solar fuel plant. A small 10cm x 10cm prototype is shown in the right panel in Figure 1. While 10x10 is a typical area established for example in the PV technology, we at Empa have panels for 20x20 systems as well. It should be possible to arrange them in larger arrays and thus obtain the suitable size for covering the roof. The photocathode material used here is iron oxide as visible light absorber deposited on indium oxide as transparent conducting oxide as current collector. The solid support is transparent glass on both sides. The counter electrode is platinum (can be replaced by cheaper copper oxide); here the hydrogen gas is generated and can be guided away to a gas storage system. This approach is fundamentally not different from natural photosynthesis (Braun 2016).

Fig. 1: (left) Photo of rain water storage and solar thermal energy installation for hot water storage on rooftop of single home in the city of Bangalore, India (Photo credit Artur Braun). (right) Solar hydrogen prototype (laboratory scale) reactor designed and manufactured at Empa. The prototype is based on iron oxide photoelectrodes and has 10cm x 10cm size (Photo credit Artur Braun & Florent Boudoire, Empa).

Currently, researchers are working worldwide for the optimization of efficiency and durability and lowering of cost for such PEC technology for solar fuel production (Thapper 2013, Braun 2016). Figure 2 (left panel) shows actual hydrogen production rates from experiments on iron oxide electrodes at Empa.

Fig. 2: (left) Evolution of the hydrogen concentration from an iron oxide based photoelectrode under alkaline conditions and 1.5 AM solar simulator conditions in the laboratory as determined by *operando* gas chromatography. (right) Asst.-Prof. Kondo-Francois Aguey-Zinsou from UNSW Australia with his hydrogen powered fuel cell bike “Hy-Cycle”, Australia’s first fuel cell powered bicycle (Photo credit UNSW).

The generated energy and power from such residential installations are - at maximum - commensurate with the solar power influx of the claimed geometrical area. This certainly sets natural limits. A potential application for mobility purposes could be the use of hydrogen fuel cell powered small vehicles, such as the “Hy-Cycle” bike shown in Figure 2 (Griffith 2016). Particularly since transportation is the obvious critical area of risk exposure, such application could be part of transition engineering of urban transportation for resilience to peak oil risks (Krumdieck 2011).

3. ADDED VALUE FOR INTEGRATIVE RISK MANAGEMENT AND URBAN RESILIENCE

The suggested residential hydrogen production and storage system shows how a single home can become independent from a fuel grid or electricity grid. It has been projected in 2002 that hydrogen from water could in the year 2020 would cost 20% more than the price of gasoline from petroleum (Bockris 2002). The storage of hydrogen fuel poses no higher risk than the storage of any other conventional fuel at the same location. Hence there is no added risk. We have to wonder how society will organize in the future. Will we favor increasing urbanization, with the result that agriculture may have to transform from rural to urban (Wakeford 2014)? Will urbanization increase, or will it reverse towards more ruralization? The solution presented here seems to be applicable for both scenarios. Accidental explosion of such small residential unit will not pose a great general danger to the public unlike a large scale production plant. Such small units would also not be attractive for enforced explosion by a strike of terror. The damage would be very limited. The media attention would be negligible. Given the considered transformation of agriculture from a rural business to an urban business (Wakeford 2014), it is likely that with the necessary land use some form of spreading out in urban areas in order to provide space for conventional farming would go along with spreading out for “hydrogen farming” (de Groot 2014) for the local supply of fuel. This approach satisfies partially the vision of urban resilience and urban sustainability.

4. CONCLUSIONS

We want to conclude with the *Future Vision*, which was expressed in the recent Food Energy Water Nexus Issue which outlined the understanding of South Africa’s most urgent sustainability challenge (Von Bormann 2014). “*It is possible to ensure that the natural resource pillars on which our society and economy rest – clean water, energy and electricity, and nutritious food – are sufficient for our needs even with rapidly growing global demand. It will take collaborative approaches, unique partnerships and new forms of dialogue. It will take more efficient production and consumption through the wider deployment of technology and informed, smart, sustainable thinking within the private and public sectors. It will require greater governance underpinned by an integrated approach to policy, planning, management and development and, critically, appropriate institutional capacity. But ultimately, it will require a shift in how we value the finite natural riches of our planet and a new approach to living sustainably within the boundaries of natural systems.*” This challenge arises not only from the South African perspective. Rather, this situation is faced by many countries on the globe and by the overwhelming majority of world population. However, given the steady growing R&D activities and policy actions for renewable and decentralized energy solutions, there is no reason for fear in view of the aforementioned challenges. Instead, there is plenty of reason for hope (de Groot 2014).

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project is financially supported by the Swiss South African Joint Research Program Project “Production of Liquid Solar Fuels from CO₂ and Water Using Renewable Energy Resources” (SNF SSAJRP <http://p3.snf.ch/Project-149031>) and the Swiss NanoTera project “Developing an efficient and cost effective hydrogen production system using sunlight and water” (SNF SHINE <http://www.nano-tera.ch/projects/367.php>), R’Equip 206021-121306, the National Research Foundation of South Africa (NRF). K.M acknowledges University of Botswana for financial support.

6. REFERENCES

- Bockris John. O’M. (2002). The origin of ideas on a Hydrogen Economy and its solution to the decay of the environment. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 27 (7-8), 731–740.
- Bora, Debajeet K.; Braun, Artur; Constable, Edwin C. (2013). “In rust we trust”. Hematite the prospective inorganic backbone for artificial photosynthesis. *Energy Environ. Sci.* 6, 407-425.
- Braun, Artur; Gaillard, Nicolas; Miller, Eric L.; Wang, Heli (2016). Editorial: “For nature is not in a hurry and mankind is”. *Journal of Materials Research*, 31 (11), 1545-1546.
- Falkenstein-Smith, R.; Wang, K.; Milcarek, R.; Ahn, J. M. (2016). ASME, Integrated Anaerobic Digester and Fuel Cell Power Generation System for Community Use. *Proceedings of the ASME 13th Fuel Cell Science, Engineering, and Technology Conference*, 2015, 5.
- Griffith, Chris (2016). From hy-cycling to self-sailing: CeBIT technology fair has it all. *The Australian*. May 5, 2016.

- de Groot, Huub (2014). Personal communication Artur Braun with Huub de Groot (Leiden University) at CNR Rome, March 21-22, 2013.
- Hu, Yelin; Bora, Debajeet K.; Boudoire, Florent; Häussler, Florian; Grätzel, Michael; Constable, Edwin C.; Braun, Artur (2013). A dip coating process for large area silicon-doped high performance hematite photoanodes. *J. Renewable Sustainable Energy* 5, 043109.
- Jung, Jin-Young; Lee, Jung-Ho (2016). Thermovoltage-driven solar hydrogen for commercialized water splitting. *SPIE Newsroom*. January 5, 2016.
- Knecht, Matthias (2013). Unfall oder Sabotage? Reformdruck auf Mexikos Erdölgiganten. *Neue Zürcher Zeitung*, 12. Februar 2013.
- Krumdieck, Susan (2011). Transition Engineering of Urban Transportation for Resilience to Peak Oil Risks. *Proceedings of the ASME International Mechanical Engineering Congress and Exposition*, 4 (Pts A and B), 387-400.
- Navarro, Carlos (2012). Fatal Explosion at Natural - Gas Plant in Tamaulipas Exposes Safety, Staffing Problems for State - Run Oil Company PEMEX. *SourceMex, Latin America Data Base*. June 29, 2012.
- Reuters (2016). Death toll rises to 32 at petrochemical plant explosion. *Reuters News Article*, April 24, 2016.
- Schuetze, Thorsten; Lee, Joong-Won; Lee, Tae-Goo (2013). Sustainable Urban (re-)Development with Building Integrated Energy, Water and Waste Systems. *Sustainability* 5 (3) ,1114-1127.
- Stratfor (2007). Mexico: Pemex Pipeline Explosion. *Stratfor Situation Reports*, October 12, 2007.
- Svensson, C; Rakhecha, P.R. (1998). Estimation of probable maximum precipitation for dams in the Hongru river catchment, China. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, 59 (1-2), 79-91.
- Thapper, Anders; Styring, Stenbjörn; Saracco, Guido; et al. (2013). Artificial Photosynthesis for Solar Fuels – an Evolving Research Field within AMPEA, a Joint Programme of the European Energy Research Alliance. *Green*, 3(1), 43 –57.
- Von Bormann, T.; Gulati, M. (2014). The Food Energy Water Nexus. Understanding South Africa’s most urgent sustainability challenge. *The Food Energy Water Nexus* 2014. Page 3. WWF-SA, South Africa.
- Wakeford, J.; M. Swilling, M. (2014). Implications of increasing world oil scarcity for national food security in South Africa, *Agrekon: Agricultural Economics Research, Policy and Practice in Southern Africa*, 53 (4), 68-91.
- Walker, Sara Louise (2013). Urban electricity systems: a UK case study. *Proceedings of the 2013 Architectural Engineering National Conference*, 614-623.